

GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE AND ITS LEGAL PERSPECTIVES IN PAKISTAN

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15916982>

Keywords

Gender-Based Violence (GBV),
Legal Framework, Pakistan,
Sociocultural Barriers, Human
Rights Violations

Article History

Received: 09 April, 2025
Accepted: 30 June, 2025
Published: 15 July, 2025

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Abstract

Gender-based violence (GBV) is a serious and widespread issue in Pakistan that affects women, children, and marginalized groups. This paper explores the legal and social challenges in addressing GBV and evaluates the laws created to protect victims. Despite having a number of legal protections such as the Pakistan Penal Code, Domestic Violence Acts, and the Anti-Rape Act, enforcement remains weak. The root causes include patriarchal norms, cultural barriers, and a lack of awareness about rights and legal processes. Most abuse victims fail to report, either because they are afraid or because of social coercion or the lack of faith in the justice system. Moreover, police and law enforcement agencies often lack proper training to handle such sensitive cases.

The study employs legal and social means to research how well the laws are performing and in what ways they should be improved. It speaks of important cases of GBV and takes a look at important laws that deal with crime, such as domestic violence, rape, honor killing, and acid attacks. Despite a few positive gains, including more serious laws on punishment and better trials there is still a wide gap to be filled. The paper concludes that real change requires not just laws but a shift in societal attitudes, better training for officials, public awareness, and stronger institutional support. Ending GBV in Pakistan demands both legal reform and social transformation to ensure safety and justice for all.

INTRODUCTION

Gender-Based Violence (GBV) may be characterized as any offense committed to a person on the basis of his or her gender. It is anchored in gender discrimination, power mistreatment, and toxic conventions. It comprises physical, sexual, psychological, and economic abuse.

GBV is based on gendered power relations and culturally and structurally endorsed gender inequalities; however, it also presents more risks and impacts the female sex predominantly and, to some

extent, the male one, as well as other genders. It is condemned as a taboo within legal and human rights and a hindrance to development within a gender mainstreaming framework. Gender-based violence is a global scourge that affects everyone, irrespective of age, social and cultural background, race, and ethnicity. In Pakistan, instances of GBV are enacted in different kinds of abuse, including domestic violence, sexual harassment, rape, honour killing, and acid throwing. Despite setting many laws to curb these

crimes, the practical implementation of such acts is deemed ruthless (Wang, 2020).

The socio-cultural setup of Pakistan is marinated in patriarchal beliefs and gender inequality, which further intensifies the challenge of controlling GBV. This paper looks towards a more critical approach to reviewing the legal infrastructure surrounding GBV in Pakistan in a way that will allow some scrutiny over effectiveness and challenges to enforcement. Law in Pakistan is a complex, multi-faceted matrix of statutory legislation, religious law, and customary practice. The Constitution of Pakistan upholds the ideal of equality and non-discrimination. Still, in practical terms, women and girls are blocked from achieving justice in most cases by systemic barriers (Ahmed, 2021). The Pakistan Penal Code does include provisions associated with diverse forms of violence against women, and children but these laws are often poorly implemented (Pakistan Penal Code, 1860). Besides this, the Domestic Violence (Prevention and Protection) Act 2012 and the Protection Against Harassment of Women at the Workplace Act are made to provide clear protection through special legislation, yet their impact remains restricted in most instances (Domestic Violence Act, 2012; Harassment at Workplace Act, 2010).

One of the significant hurdles in addressing GBV in Pakistan relates to a lack of awareness and understanding among the general public and law enforcement agencies concerning the prevailing laws. Many victims do not know their legal rights or the systems and support provided by the state to protect their rights (Aurat Foundation, 2018). Additionally, most of these law enforcement officials have not been trained and oriented on how to address issues of GBV effectively. This knowledge and capacity gap both foster the underreporting of incidents of GBV and contribute to the inadequate response to reported cases (Amnesty International, 2020).

Patriarchal culture in Pakistan was one of the main reasons behind gender-based violence (GBV). These norms bring violence against women and girls. Of them, in some circumstances, the victims are made to be scorned and excluded by society to avoid getting any assistance. The issue of honor is very prominent in Pakistan, where any relational loss of it leads to violent outcomes against women. These cultural

practices justify GBV reasoning, even though there is a legal provision against it (UN Women, 2020).

Over recent years, there have been some positive developments in the legal and policy framework for addressing GBV in Pakistan. Recently, the reform of the Anti-Rape Ordinance in 2020, with a plethora of others focused on making the trial process of rape incidents more time-efficient and protective toward the victim, is a move toward the right path. Still, its effectiveness depends on the application of the act. There is so much talk on social change, but it has remained anecdotal. These concerns will be taken into detail by this paper in the legal analyses of the situation with GBV in Pakistan, which comes with suggestions for improvements in the response through law to this critical issue.

Background of the Study

GBV is a complex and recurrent form of violence in territories of the world, and today, it is among the most egregious violations of the fundamental human rights of people, especially women and girls. In their survey, the United Nations believes that one out of every three women in the world experiences physical or sexual abuse in their lifetime, most of it by their husband or partner (UN Women, 2021). In Pakistan, the issue of GBV is particularly significant due to the culture and practice of female subordination, as well as the inadequate legal framework for the protection of women's rights. According to the PDHS (2017-18) survey information, 28% of EME with 15-49 have faced physical hypnosis, of which 34% were the victims of her husband.

The legal protection instruments for GBV in Pakistan include the Pakistan Protection of Women (Criminal Laws Amendment Act 2006), the Domestic Violence (Prevention and Protection) Acts, and the Anti-Rape (Investigation and Trial) Act 2021. But owing to sociocultural issues, poor compliance with the laws in question, and inadequate institutions, the aforementioned laws do not have the desired effects. However, cases of honor killings, even though they fall under the prohibited category due to the Anti-Honor Killing Laws (Amendment) Act 2016, still occur. In as much as there has been an improvement in the reporting of cases, in the year 2022 alone, over 400 documented cases were reported in the country (Human Rights Commission of Pakistan, 2022). They

show how there is a difference between passing laws and the practice of the same; this underscores the need for social and organizational transformation. Moreover, political conflicts, state instability, and terrorism have resulted in the increased rate of GBV, in addition to the local cultural norms that are common to punish women or force them to be silent for the protection of family honor or to follow the male-dominated culture. These include child marriage, dowry-related violence, and restriction of movement results in physical and psychological violence. For instance, while the Sindh Child Marriage Restraint Act 2013 stipulated marriageable age at 18, according to UNICEF (2021), 21% of Pakistani girls are still married before their 18th birthday. This has helped in bringing out the problem of describing the fight against GBV through law reform and/or reform of social culture. Such cultural factors, along with the prevailing culture of stigmatization and fear that encompasses the act of reporting GBV, are already an obstacle to the victim receiving justice a challenge that, under legal reform, the effort to eliminate impunity, raise awareness of GBV, and enhance systems of support for affected victims needs only a legal solution.

Aims and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this research is to take an uncomplicated look at the laws that exist in Pakistan under the topic of GBV. Relatively, it centers on the awareness of the

various existing laws as well as how efficient their enforcement is and challenges as encountered by the victims in the process of seeking justice. It also shows problems or deficiencies in the legal system.” First, the study assesses the functionality of the already enacted laws on combating GBV and any changes or emergences in GBV laws.

Methodological Concerns

This paper aims to critically discuss the challenges of responding to GBV in Pakistan, utilizing an interpretive study that is distinct from the legal and social context of the topic (Wiesner, 2022). The study incorporates both qualitative and doctrinal approaches (Pattaro, 2006) to examine the practices of enforcing GBV laws, the challenges faced by victims, and the existing legal voids. To this end, the study brings together literature on the subject and presents an understanding of the social relationship between GBV survivors and the justice system in Pakistan. A historical background is also considered to review the development of the legislation on GBV. While it is impossible to review all laws connected with GBV, the paper concentrates on some of the main legislative acts that influenced the experience of protection and assistance for victims of GBV. This approach enables an enhanced assessment of the impact of these laws and the suggestions on the response to GBV in Pakistan in legal systems.

Legal Jurisprudence

Table 1: Notable Cases of Gender-Based Violence and Women's Rights in Pakistan

Case Study	Year	Background	Incident	Legal Proceedings	Outcome
Saima Waheed	1996	Married against her family's wishes	Father claimed she was mentally unstable to annul marriage	Lahore High Court ruled in favor of Saima	Landmark decision for women's rights, affirmed women's right to marital choices
Samia Sarwar	1999	Sought divorce from abusive husband	Shot dead by hitman hired by her family	Minimal legal consequences for family due to their influence	Highlighted issue of honor killings and need for legal reforms
Fakhra Younus	2000	Victim of acid attack by estranged husband	Husband threw acid on her face and body	Husband never convicted due to political connections	Led to the Acid Control and Acid Crime Prevention Act in 2011, committed suicide in 2012

Sabatina James	2001	Faced threats of honor killing after converting to Christianity	Fled home and went into hiding	No formal legal proceedings in Pakistan, significant attention in Austria	Became advocate for women's rights and freedom of religion
Mukhtar Mai	2002	Gang-raped as honor revenge ordered by tribal council	Public gang rape	Initial convictions overturned by Lahore High Court, national and international outrage	Became symbol of resistance, established school and women's shelter
Asma Jahangir	2002	Prominent human rights lawyer and activist	Attacked by religious extremists	Attack drew widespread condemnation	Continued advocacy for human rights until her death in 2018
Benazir Bhutto	2007	First female Prime Minister of Pakistan	Assassinated in suicide attack	Investigation marred by controversy and political interference	Her legacy influences political discourse, remembered for promoting women's rights and democracy
Kainat Soomro	2007	Kidnapped and gang-raped by four men	Family faced threats and social ostracism	Accused acquitted, continued harassment and threats	Highlighted challenges for rape victims in judicial system
Shazia Masih	2010	12-year-old domestic servant found dead	Visible signs of physical abuse	Employer acquitted due to political influence and lack of proper investigation	Highlighted plight of domestic workers and challenges in seeking justice
Sharmeen Obaid-Chinoy	2012	Filmmaker highlighting gender-based violence	Won Academy Award for "Saving Face"	Documentary contributed to passage of Acid Control and Acid Crime Prevention Act	Raised awareness about gender-based violence in Pakistan
Malala Yousafzai	2012	Advocate for girls' education	Shot in the head by Taliban gunman	Perpetrators sentenced to life imprisonment	Continued advocacy, youngest Nobel Prize laureate, established Malala Fund
Rukhsana Bibi	2013	Attacked by husband and in-laws due to dowry dispute	Beaten with sticks, acid poured on her face	Husband and in-laws arrested and charged	Highlighted issue of dowry-related violence, perpetrators sentenced to long prison terms
Farzana Parveen	2014	Stoned to death by family for marrying of her choice	Attacked outside Lahore High Court	Family members arrested and charged	Led to increased pressure on Pakistan to address honor killings and protect women's rights
Kasur Child Abuse Scandal	2015	A village in Kasur, Punjab, where a gang had been exploiting children for years by recording videos of	Hundreds of children were sexually abused, and videos were recorded. Families were threatened	Multiple FIRs were filed. Investigations led to the arrest of several gang members.	The court convicted two main perpetrators to life imprisonment and imposed heavy fines, but many families still seek justice for broader accountability.

		abuse and using them to blackmail families.	with the release of these videos.		
Khadija Siddiqui	2016	Attacked by classmate for rejecting his advances	Stabbed 23 times	Initially acquitted, public outrage led to eventual conviction	Highlighted challenges for victims of gender-based violence in seeking justice
Qandeel Baloch	2016	Social media celebrity murdered by brother	Strangled to death in honor killing	Brother confessed, sentenced to life imprisonment	Increased awareness and advocacy against honor killings
Zeenat Rafiq	2016	Murdered by mother for marrying without family consent	Tied to cot, doused with kerosene, set on fire	Mother confessed, sentenced to death	Led to calls for stronger legal measures to prevent honor killings
Faisalabad Abuse Case	2017	A young boy working as a domestic servant in Faisalabad faced severe abuse from his employer, including physical violence and starvation.	The boy was beaten severely and denied food for several days, leading to his hospitalization.	The employer was arrested after public outrage and media coverage. The case was taken to court under Pakistan's child protection laws.	The employer received a five-year prison sentence and a fine, but the case highlighted ongoing issues in monitoring domestic labor conditions for children.
Sargodha Trafficking Case	2018	A case involving a network trafficking young boys from rural areas to urban centers for sexual exploitation and forced labor.	Multiple boys were abducted and subjected to abuse and forced labor under inhumane conditions.	A joint task force was formed to dismantle the trafficking network. Several arrests were made, and rescue operations freed numerous victims.	Key perpetrators were sentenced to life imprisonment, and the case underscored the need for improved tracking and prevention mechanisms for child trafficking in Pakistan.
Farishta Mohmand	2019	10-year-old girl abducted, raped, and murdered	Body found in forest near Islamabad	Police officers suspended for negligence	Ongoing investigation, highlighted need for better protection and reforms in police and judicial system
Ahmed Case (Karachi)	2019	A 10-year-old boy in Karachi was subjected to severe physical and sexual abuse by a neighbor who had a history of criminal behavior.	Ahmed was abducted, sexually abused, and left unconscious in a deserted area.	Police arrested the suspect based on eyewitness accounts and forensic evidence.	The perpetrator was sentenced to life imprisonment, but the case highlighted the need for more robust child protection laws and better victim support systems.
Noor Mukadam	2021	Daughter of former diplomat murdered by friend	Brutally murdered	Investigation ongoing, drew widespread media coverage	Sparked national debate on violence against women and need for legal reforms

Legislation for Addressing Gender-Based Violence in Pakistan

1. The Pakistan Penal Code, 1860

The Pakistan Penal Code, 1860 involves many sections that deal with gender-based violence and provide protection as well as justice to women, who are the

most common victims. These provisions can be said to tackle a myriad of gender-based violence offences, and some of the most important areas are the offences of physical abuse and assault. Likewise, Sections 337A to 337L refer to the punishment of any harm done with the intention to cause hurt if such harm results

in disfigurement or disability, familiar in domestic or other public violence cases. Sexual offences are dealt with in strict provisions of this code; this is in Sections 375 and 376, where Section 375 defines rape comprehensively, and Section 376 prescribes severe punishments. For additional grave circumstances like gang rape or violation of minors, the sanctions are much more severe. Further, section 354A carries provisions that treat acts of pulling or stripping the clothes of a woman to awaken her modesty as grievous crimes, as the above sections reflect the state's attitude to fight against such grievous crimes. Pursuant to this provision, protection against workplace harassment, street harassment, and similar acts of intimidation goes. This is not expressly covered under a section, but sometimes there are sections like Section 337, for causing hurt, and Section 506 for criminal intimidation, under which domestic violence falls. The PPC also addresses honor killings; this is more like cultural issues. Section 310A makes the inhuman practice of making women marriage payments (vani or swara) unlawful. Section 311 removes the opportunity for those involved in honor killings to avoid prosecution by seeking and receiving the forgiveness of the victim's family; this section treats such a crime as murder under Section 302. Kidnapping and trafficking are crimes outlawed by Section 364A, where abducting a child under the age of fourteen with the intention of using the child for any unlawful purpose is prohibited, and Section 366 bars the abducting of women. These sections relate to the aspects of human trafficking and forced exploitation, particularly of women and children. Introduction of section 336B to ensure heinous acts of acid attacks are addressed with a stiffer penalty of life imprisonment or a severe one will be given to offenders. As for this provision, it is intended as a measure to counter such savage attacks, which usually inflict women and leave them physically and psychologically scarred for the rest of their lives. The last one is forced marriage, including marriage as a form of punishment for crime or as a compensation is defined in Section 498A. This has a provision that penalises the practice of forcing women into marital relationships they do not desire, it provides for punishment for the culprit, and it also guarantees the right of women. The above provisions demonstrate how the PPC is a holistic law in dealing with gender-based violence in Pakistan.

2. The Child Marriage Restraint Act, 1929

The Child Marriage Restraint Act, 1929 prevents child marriages and tackle gender-based violence. Under Section 2, a child is defined as any male under the age of twenty-one years and any female under the age of eighteen years. Section 3 is on the prohibition of child marriage, where any adult male contracting marriage on behalf of a child, parents or guardians of the child, or any person performing the marriage ceremony commits an offense. Section 4 provides penalties for violations of the provisions of the Act and the regulations made thereunder, which would be imprisonment for a term not exceeding one month, a fine, or both. Section 6 enables courts to act on offences as presented by the complainant, parents, guardians, or any public officer. Thus, through preventing child marriages, the Act addresses gender-based violence.

3. The Muslim Family Laws Ordinance, 1961

The Muslim Family Laws Ordinance, 1961, has occurrences of some of the other angles of GBV contained in some of the measures it has taken to protect women and guarantee their equality with men in family affairs. Section 4 safeguards the rights of inheriting the effects of an intestate by a grandson, especially females, where the sons had been discriminated against financially. According to section 5, marriages should be registered, and since some people are being forced to marry or are abused by their partners, then these documents come in handy. In section 6, which deals with polygamy, consent is required from the wife already married and the Arbitration Council to avoid issues of emotional and financial exploitation. Section 7 sets procedural regularity of divorce: notifications and a 90-day waiting period, preserving women from abusive divorces. The code also spells out in section 9 the responsibility to support one's wife and children so as not to use them as objects of financial cruelty. Although the ordinance does not directly deal with GBV, these provisions are instrumental to the legal framework of women's rights and positive struggle to contain an abuse of family members.

4. The Constitution of Islamic Republic of Pakistan, 1973

The Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan, 1973, grants relevant principles of addressing gender-based violence in terms of rights, equalities, and dignity. Article 4 establishes equality, and Article 9 provides security to each and every individual by not permitting anyone from harming life or liberty. Article 14 of the Charter protects human dignity and prohibits torture and inhuman treatment—it is, in another dimension, a direct contradiction to acts of violence like abuse or harassment. Article 25 provides the right to equal protection before the law, and section (3) of the article cancels sex discrimination, though it allows the state to adopt special measures in favor of women or children. Further, Articles 26 and 27 have prohibited discrimination in including rights to access public places and employment, which furthermore prevent structural violence. Article 34 requires the full integration of women in the nation and protection against gender-based violence. The best interpretation of this article is that section 35 prescribes it as the duty of the state to safeguard the sanctity of the family, the female gender, and the children, which corroborates the fight against domestic violence. On the same note, the state is obliged by Article 37 (e) to protect women in workplaces and eliminate social evils. Altogether these sections make gender-based violence a constitutional violation and clause a constitutional imperative asserting the rights of women to be protected and empowered.

5. The Enforcement of Hudood Ordinances, 1979

The Enforcement of Hudood Ordinances, 1979, brought changes that helped reform gender-based violence cases under the Offence of Zina (Enforcement of Hudood) Ordinance, 1979. These articles are Section 4, which deals with the prohibition of zina, which means adultery or fornication, and Section 5, which explains the hadd punishment for zina. Rape (zina-bil-jabr) is addressed under section 6, which states the forced sexual intercourse but lacks the evidence of penetration and extremely stringent conditions of proof under section 8. This section requires four adult male Muslim witnesses of good character to testify to the act, which makes convictions

tricky. If these evidential standards were not met, the case would fall under tazir, under Section 10, which offers less severe punishment like imprisonment. However, women who accused someone of rape but did not prove it were liable to be charged with zina under Section 7 and could face various punishments, including flogging or stoning if the case was in the realm of hadd. This put so much pressure on rape victims that so many of them were unable to report their cases to court in an attempt to seek justice because they would be arrested and perceived as criminals by society.

6. The Qanun e Shahadat Ordinance, 1984

The Qanun-e-Shahadat Ordinance, 1984, governs the rules of evidence in Pakistan and includes several provisions relevant to cases of gender-based violence. Article 3 establishes that all individuals are competent to testify unless disqualified by law, recognising women as witnesses. However, societal biases can impact the weight of their testimony. Article 17(2) is particularly significant in cases of zina and zina-bil-jabr (rape), requiring the testimony of four adult male Muslim witnesses for hadd punishments, a requirement that creates significant barriers in proving rape, as such acts rarely have witnesses. In tazir cases, the evidentiary requirements are less stringent, allowing women and non-Muslims to testify. Article 59 permits the use of expert testimony, such as forensic evidence, which is critical in sexual violence cases where physical evidence like DNA can establish non-consensual acts. Article 121 places the burden of proof on the prosecution, requiring guilt to be established beyond reasonable doubt, a standard that often proves challenging for survivors of gender-based violence due to societal stigma. Article 129 allows courts to draw presumptions, but delays in reporting rape may unfairly affect the victim's credibility. Articles 151 and 153 allow cross-examination to challenge witnesses' credibility, which can subject victims to intrusive questioning about their character, deterring them from seeking justice. Lastly, Article 164 permits the use of modern technology and forensic techniques, such as DNA evidence or surveillance footage, offering vital support in proving allegations of gender-based violence.

7. The Women in Distress and Detention Fund Act,1996

The Women in Distress and Detention Fund Act,1996 aims at giving financial legal aid to women who are in helpless condition specially women violence by men. The Women in Distress and Detention Fund set in section 3 provides a fund to women in distress, women in shelters, or women trapped in violence or exploitation. Purposes of the fund that have described in section 4: a) provide legal assistance, b) provide medical treatment, c) offer psychological counseling and rehabilitation, d) guarantee safety for women and girls and prevent further abuse. It vouch for the operational realities of suffering women, it leads to formulated way to address female predicament.

8. The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act,2004

The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act,2004 has brought some changes in relation to GBV with heightened foci on practices like Badla-e-Sulh and honor killing. It inserted Section 310A, which dealt with any act of providing a woman in marriage or otherwise in connection with any dispute, and its punishment was imprisonment for a term of three to ten years. Amending the laws effectively was likewise done to delimit the offenses made in the name or on the pretext of honor under Section 299 of the PPC. In order to enhance the accountability, section 311 was amended, and according to the new law, the court can award a death sentence of 10 to 14 years of imprisonment in murder cases, now known as Qatle-Amd, committed in the name of honor even if the victim family has pardoned the accused. Likewise, Section 338E of the PPC was also amended to decouple or ask for prohibition when one of the offenses could be waived or compounded in honor-related cases. These amendments are conceived in order to help to increase legal measures against the violators of the rights of women with regard to honor crimes and cultural violence against them and to protect the women's rights and dignity within this legal framework.

9. The Protection of Women (Criminal Laws Amendment) Act,2006

The Protection of Women (Criminal Laws Amendment) Act, 2006 was a landmark to change the

laws of Pakistan and to end or reduce violence against women. The Act further amended sections 375 and 376 of the PPC and increased the listing and parameters of the rape while keeping the death penalty and life imprisonment for those committing heinous sexual offenses such as gang raping or raping in custody. Sec 496A legalized giving false accusations of fornication, making it harder for individuals to misuse such allegations against women. The Act also changed the Hudood Ordinances, shifting cases of zina and qazf to the PPC to ensure trials were done based on the principles of evidence and procedural protections of the accused. The Qanun-e-Shahadat Order (QSO), 1984, also under section 151(4), banned the practice of regarding women as From Array, the general character of the prosecutrix being in question—even in the cases of rape and sexual violence, she cannot be subjected to character assassination. Furthermore, Section 509 of the PPC was enhanced to respond to sexual harassment in the course of performing a lawful activity where the accused committed an act that is immoral and indecent and is likely to insult the dignity of a woman. Finally, some reforms, which were actually unfavorable for the victims, include the introduction of Section 402-B of the CrPC that placed stringent conditions to offer bails to those accused of rape and sexual assault so that they cannot escape punishment. Altogether, these changes are intended to prevent GBV, guarantee equal and non-discriminatory monstrous treatment of survivors, and protect legislated female decency.

10. The Protection Against Harassment of Women at the Workplace Act,2010

The Protection Against Harassment of Women at Workplace Act, 2010, aims to protect women against different types of harassment at the workplace and also address issues of gender-based violence. It gives a sweeping meaning to 'harassment,' which covers sexual advances, discriminating conduct, or behaviors that make the working environment unbearably uncomfortable for the targeted employee. The Act regulates activities across all sectors of employment, both public and private, for employees, employers, and persons engaged under a contract of service. Employers are required to set up complaint procedures in matters of harassment and inquiry

committees that should include people of the two genders in order to thoroughly and secretly investigate any complaints. The Act also provides measures from reprimand to dismissal, fines, and other remedies for harassment and GBV. An ombudsman can be used for an appeal in situations when victims of assaults and aggressive behavior want to make sure they have been treated fairly by the courts. Any form of reprisal against complainants or witnesses is prohibited, making reporting safe. Also, the employers are mandated to display a Code of Conduct designed to feed into the Act and should organize awareness and training sessions to discourage workplace harassment. These provisions combined afford protection to women, discourage the acts of violence against them, and encourage employer equity.

11. The Prevention of Anti-Women Practices (Criminal Law Amendment) Act, 2011

The Prevention of Anti-Women Practices (Criminal Law Amendment) Act, 2011 regulates gender-based violence to control several anti-women practices that leads prejudice and exploitation of women. To eradicate this unwanted practice the act has abolished the traditional methods of resolving conflicts and controversies same as swara or vani the law provides punishment in form of three to seven years imprisonment and 500,000 PKR fine. There is also forced marriage mentioned under the Act and other practices such as marrying women to the Quran (Haq Bakhshish); anyone is found guilty of this law will be liable of imprisonment for a term not exceeding 3 years or to the same depth of punitive fine. Also, it provides with those who deprive share of women by cheating or force which makes it obligatory to send such person to jail for five to ten years with a fine of one million PKR. It is the vision of the Act to bring better responsibility for such crimes by modifying the provisions of the PPC and the CrPC. Cumulatively it means that these provisions try to help women legally stay out of harms way and shield them from practices which are based on gender related physical violence.

12. The Acid Control and Acid Crime Prevention Act,2011

The Acid Control and Acid Crime Prevention Act, 2011, is a legal instrument aimed at tackling acid violence. These changes were enacted by the Pakistan

Penal Code (PPC) and the code of criminal procedure (CrPC) through the new specified Act of the acid attack. The Act pursuant to the PPC Section 336A entails elements of the offense of hurt caused by dangerous means or substances such as acid, while Section 336B provided for the enforcement of severe penalties for persons who commit offenses under that Section. The accused found guilty of acid attacks are awarded life imprisonment or a minimum of fourteen years' imprisonment and are also fined not less than one million rupees.

13. The National Commission on the Status of Women Act,2012

The National Commission on the Status of Women Act,2012 provides for the establishment of the National Commission on the Status of Women (NCSW) as an independent institution for the protection of women's rights, especially implementing control measures against gender-based violence (GBV). The Act defines the supremacy and missions of the Commission to include advancing the constitutional mandates of women, monitoring and enforcing compliance with international legal instruments like CEDAW, and offering recommendations for legal and policy changes to address GBV. Major activities covered by the Commission include scrutiny and monitoring of laws, policies, and mechanisms on GBV and violence against women activists'; public awareness-raising for societal transformation; think tank roles; and collection of information/data on violence against women. It also openly follows cases dealing with GBV survivors to guarantee they obtain justice. The Commission has the jurisdiction to investigate violations of rights of women, produce evidence, and request reports from any government department on GBV occurrences. It operates in partnership with federal and provincial governments and departments, the police, non-governmental organizations, and civil society with the view to building equal normative frameworks for dealing with GBV across the country. By means of annual and special reports, it makes recommendations for the amendments of legislation and policies and presents issues concerning GBV to the government's actions. All these provisions make it possible for the NCSW to act and prevent acts of GBV and protect the rights of women.

14. The Sindh Domestic Violence (Prevention and Protection) Act,2013

The Sindh Domestic Violence (Prevention and Protection) Act, 2013 is an empowering piece of legislation that offers protection against GBV within the home. This means that domestic violence is comprehensively described to include physical, emotional, psychological, sexual, and economic violence. This goes a long way in acknowledging the fact that gender-based violence is not a simple, one-faceted issue. The Act covers all close relationships, including spouses, blood relations, cohabitants, and those involving children and their guardians. Protection includes the formation of the Protection Committees and the selection of the Protection Officers who are supposed to help survivors by organizing medical attention, legal aid, and shelter. They are able to apply for protective orders in order to stop the use of violence on them, apply for residential orders to guarantee safe shelter, and get a lawyer for advocacy of the case. Measures taken against offenders are arrest and imprisonment, imposition of fines, and reimbursement of damages to the survivor. The Act focuses on the issues of confidentiality; it establishes the shelter homes and medical and psychological aid of the victims. It also reaches out to the public with the sensitization through training of law enforcement officials on how to effectively handle gender-based violence cases. This way the Act protects the wounded, especially women, helps them free themselves from violence, and seek justice in a physical, emotional, and financial battle with the perpetrators.

15. The Balochistan Domestic Violence (Prevention and Protection) Act,2014

The Balochistan Domestic Violence (Prevention and Protection) Act 2014 is a legal system created in order to prevent and protect against gender-based violence in the domestic sphere. It gives a detailed focus on domestic violence: physical, psychological, verbal, emotional, sexual, and economic powerlessness. The Act also appreciates the role of preventing violence against women, children, and other vulnerable persons and offers for the formulation of protection committees and protection officers for the same. Some of the legal interventions include protection orders issued by the court and the protection of a

victim from further ill-treatment. Risk assessment, safe shelter homes for women and children, voluntary counselling and reporting facilities for the victims, and medical facilities for survivors are other measures provided in the Act besides the penalties for the offender to prevent further incidence of violence. Also, it requires awareness-raising activities and police and social services training to increase their ability to handle gender-based violence efficiently. Limitations to the right [of access to information] include restrictions for use in protecting the identity of victims and monitoring and evaluation mechanisms for assessment of compliance and effectiveness of the law.

16. The Punjab Protection of Women against Violence Act,2016

The Punjab Protection of Women Against Violence Act of 2016 is a legal mechanism for combating and preventing violence against women in Punjab, Pakistan. It is as general as encompassing physical aggression, mental maltreatment, sexual abuse, financial misuse, attempts to control, and use of technology to harm. The Act also guarantees women's right to live in their homes without being thrown out or intimidated, and it permits the courts to make protection orders that bar offenders that are a menace to victims. Preliminary orders made within a residence order can also direct that victims must be housed in an alternative manner if necessary. The law also includes provisions for an award of monetary damages for medical expenses and loss of earnings and general damages of violence. For efficient support, protection centers and shelter homes are formed to give medicosocial, legal, and psychological aid. Women Protection Officers are supposed to provide means for accessing these centers and to guarantee compliance with court orders. Failure or breach of these measures is sharply punishable by either imprisonment or fines. Additionally, GPS tracking is adopted for the other offenders with more grave crimes in the course of their supervision. This legislation establishes a willingness to prevent violence against women, to provide legal frameworks and justice systems for the woman who is a victim, as well as afford her an opportunity to be protected, receive legal protection, and be made whole.

17. The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act,2016
The Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2016 brought quite a lot of changes regarding gender-based offenses, especially honor killings and sexual offenses. It was an amendment to the Pakistan Penal Code (PPC) and the Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC) to eliminate the legal technicalities through which the honor killing offenders used to get acquitted by obtaining the kin's pardon from the victim. It prescribes a non-discharge eligibility of 25 years of imprisonment for honor killings even if she forgives the culprit. The Act also enlarged the definition of rape to cover a wide range of other forced acts and required DNA sampling on any rape case in order to support real investigation evidence collection. Rape and sexual offense trials are conducted behind closed doors to shield the victim's identity, and female survivors must be taken through the statement-making process in the presence of a female police officer or a family member to willingly consent to the process. These provisions seek to try to bring more severe penalties for the violators, protect the integrity of the victims, and improve the efficiency of combating gender-based violence.

18. The Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act,2018
The Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act 2018 also contains sections that ensure the protection of trans persons from discrimination, harassment, or violence and respect their rights and dignity. Section 4 closes the door on discrimination against persons based on their gender identities, especially in education, the workplace, and health, among other aspects of public life. Section 5 also states that one cannot harass, or authorize someone else to harass, another person either in or outside a home on the ground of sex, gender identity, or gender expression. Section 6 requires the government to set up protection centers and safe households as well as transitional homes where transgender persons can be rescued, protected, and provided with services such as medical services, psychological counseling, and education for persons above eighteen years. Section 17 makes it an offense to force a transgender person to beg and is penalized by imprisonment and fine. Furthermore, Chapter VI provides enforcement procedures that any transgender person who feels that his/her rights were violated can report to the Federal

Ombudsman, the National Commission for the Status of Women, or the National Commission on Human Rights. Taken together, these provisions seek to protect the transgender persons from gender-based violence and marginalization in society.

19. The Juvenile Justice System Act,2018
The Juvenile Justice System Act,2018 contains specific provisions aimed at protecting juveniles, particularly in cases involving GBV. Section 3 provides legal representation to juveniles or child victims of offenses at the state's expense where the right is to be informed within 24 hours of custody. Section 17 of the law aimed at protecting female juveniles does not allow any male officer to arrest or investigate females, and in case the juvenile female is released on probation, she should be supervised by female officers. Female juveniles are also to be restricted to female juvenile rehabilitation centers in order to avoid more harassment or even victimization. Under Section 16 of the Act, juveniles detained in custody are protected from abuse in the form of GBV in the form of corporal punishment or forced labor or degrading treatment. Section 13 is aimed at protecting a young person's dignity and his/her privacy since it is unlawful to publish anything that is likely to lead to the identification of the juvenile in any legal process. Further, Sections 20 and 22 provide for the setting up of observation homes and juvenile rehabilitation centers and the separation of facilities for female juveniles. Taken collectively, these provisions are meant to protect juveniles from GBV, the rights of these vulnerable persons, as well as their rehabilitation and reintegration into society.

20. The Zainab Alert, Response, and Recovery Act,2020
The Zainab Alert, Response, and Recovery Act, 2020, of Pakistan legislates the necessary measures for prevention, reporting, rescue, treatment, and justice in cases of abduction, abuse, and sexual exploitation of children with special reference to little girls. The Act provides that there should be an establishment of the Zainab Alert, Response, and Recovery Agency, abbreviated as ZARRA, to alert, respond to, and recover any missing children. It operationalizes a child as anyone below the age of 18 years and puts the police on the spot for their failure to register FIRs on missing

children. The Act raises the stakes for criminals who are convicted of perpetrating either the abduction or abuse of children. As for ZARRA, another objective is to use technology, for instance, by developing an application based on a database that would enhance reporting and tracking of such work. Also, there is focus on the campaigns and awareness creation, and in this regard, a helpline number, 1099, was set to encourage reporting. The Act also makes provisions for the administration of care and recovery for children who have been taken: principles of recovery including psychosocial recovery. These measures combine to protect children, particularly girls, from any form of violence and ensure quick delivery of justice and compensation where a child is abducted or sexually assaulted.

21. The Anti-Rape (Investigation and Trial) Act,2021

The Anti-Rape (Investigation and Trial) Act,2021 is a significant legislative framework designed to combat sexual violence .The Act requires the setting up of courts to try the cases faster and Special Sexual Offences Investigation Units (SSOUIs) in every district to deal with the cases with personnel of the right caliber. Anti-Rape Crisis Cells (ARCCs) are intended to give quick, coordinated mediation, lawful and therapeutic, to survivors. It focuses on the application of the advanced scientific methods, like the DNA tests, improving the collection of evidence. Some ways in which the identity privileges the survivors are maintaining their privacy and dignity, including in-camera trials and confidentiality of the identity. There exist the so-called legal aid services for the rays, and penalties for slander are also assigned to protect the purity of the given process. A National Sex Offenders Register is created in order to have a record of the convicted offenders. It is also for the education of law enforcement and the judiciary in the handling of the cases as required despite sensitivity. These provisions combined intend to develop a sensitive and helpful system for dealing with gendered brutality in Pakistan.

22. The Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Domestic Violence Act,2021

The Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Domestic Violence Act, 2021 also aims at preventing, protecting, and dealing

with gender-based violence in domestic settings. The Act establishes domestic violence as physical, psychological/emotional, sexual, or economic violence of women by a domestic partner. This involves orders such as protection orders, residence orders, and monetary remedies for the protection of the victims. Each District Protection Committee’s role is to offer emergency protection and support and to act as a database. It is shown that service providers such as registered organizations and governmental facilities are very significant in order to provide legal, medical, and financial support for the victims. Legal measures under the Act provide the ability to the courts to give interim and protection orders and penalties for violations, which may result in imprisonment of the guilty and fines. Further, it also envisages the setting up of the helplines, shelter homes, and social awareness program for the public and official to crack the domestic violence cases. The submitted Act is complemented by the Domestic Violence Against Women (Prevention and Protection) Rules, 2022, to stipulate how implementation shall occur. This means that the existence of this legislation marks a positive move in the fight against gender-based violence in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

23. The Protection against Harassment of Women at the Workplace (Amendment) Act,2022

The Protection against Harassment of Women at the Workplace (Amendment) Act 2022 enhances the definition of parameters under gender-based violence and comes to increase the efficacy of such provisions. It does so neither by limiting the concept of ‘employee’ but rather by explicitly adding regular, contractual, part-time, freelance workers, domestic workers, and others, to mention but a few, which guarantees disparate employment types coverage. Various forms of business management common in the contemporary world, such as online and remote employers, as well as households employing workers, are included in the concept of “employer.” Thus, the proponents of the ‘workplace’ have evolved this term to mean any place that professional services are provided, including cyberspace, school campuses, and even outdoors whenever individuals are contracted to work. The harassment is understood not only as sexual propositions and demands for a favor but also

as discrimination based on gender and stalking in social networks. Employers must set up inquiry committees, make sure the parties are represented fairly within those committees, and post a copy of the Code of Conduct. The Act requires that action be taken by the perpetrators ranging from rebuke to discharge and permits compensation for the victims. It also designates ombudspersons at federal and provincial levels for complaint inquiries as well as appeals. Altogether it is envisaged that all these provisions ensure a better and safe working environment free from harassment and tackles gender-based violence in the workplace.

Discussion

In Pakistan, gender equality and the protection of women's rights are guaranteed by the Constitution, but the reality is often different due to societal attitudes and challenges with law enforcement. The Constitution of Foster 1999 asserts that no citizen shall be discriminated against and every citizen shall be protected by the law. Ahmad & Bhatti, 2023 However, due to cultures and societal norms, women do not fully exercise these rights. However, gender-based violence remains rife in Pakistan, and multiple women encounter challenges when seeking legal redress because of gendered violence as envisaged by the PPC (Khaliq & Sultan, 2022). For instance, sections under the PPC pertain to offences such as assault and rape, but the PPC laws traditionally are often inadequately enforced, through problems such as underreporting of the cases, slowed court procedures, and inefficient investigation.

The act more specifically affecting the country's women folk is the Domestic Violence Act of 2012, which was intended to shield victims of abuse currently with implementation challenges. Some of the challenges include: Firstly, low awareness about green chemistry; secondly, the limited resources or funding that is available for green chemistry research; and finally, resistance to change from some stakeholder or members of society (Nawaz et al., 2022). To this end, more information to the people, proper training to the police officers, and more or enhanced mechanisms in the prosecution for the victims are imperative. The Workplace Harassment Act (2010) was enacted to protect women at work, but many workplaces don't implement it well. However,

in order for the law to serve its intended purpose, constant supervision and enhanced repercussions for violations of the law are paramount (Mahmood & Ahmad, 2007).

Even at this, we observe certain signs of social improvement, such as the Anti-Rape Ordinance (2020) and the revamping of the Hudood Ordinances (1979). The Anti-Rape Ordinance introduced new trials for rape offences and the sex offender list to fasten the trials and protect the women. However, for these changes to take effect, there must be collaboration between law enforcement and the judiciary, while there is the need for proper training and sensitisation (Zahid, 2024). The Hudood Ordinances, which were meant to make the legal system more Islamic, were usually prejudiced against women, especially in regards to zina and qazf. Current revamps attempt to eradicate such discriminations, but there are a lot of barriers through which women need to cross in order to seek justice (Khaliq & Sultan, 2022).

The most relevant and important legislation to the serious crime of acid attack, especially women, is the Acid Control Act 2011. Any person found guilty is punished severely, while the sale of acid is also restricted. However, there are still some problems, like providing better control for sales of acid and further assistance to the victims in order to make them receive medical and psychological help (von Werlhof, 2014). In the same way, the Criminal Law Amendment Act (2016) enhances the legal procedure through which a rape is prosecuted through using forensic evidence, police by female officers, and shielding the identity of the complainant. However, for the law to work effectively, then law enforcement officers have to be trained (Ahmad & Bhatti, 2023).

The Protection of Women Act (2006) is one of the most exhaustive laws of Pakistan for women against gender-based violence such as forced marriages and honour killing. While the former can be considered progress since historically there were no laws against curtailing media freedom, the latter weakens its effectiveness and requires a change of culture among the Central Asian countries, where media freedom is still an undefined reality (Nawaz et al., 2022). It is good though that in recent years there have been some improvements on this, like passing the Anti-Rape Ordinance 2020 to that effect, but it will be a gradual

proactivity change, not a one-time fix. It will also require the government, civil society, and international organisations in the long term to address barriers motivated by social and cultural factors; Periodic reporting: The government, civil society, and international organisations are requested to report periodically in three years time on the progress of this paper.

While these are identifiable as progressive legislation, there is a long way to go in making change that actually means something for the women of Pakistan that requires dismantling culture and society itself in the country.

Conclusion

Dealing with gender-based violence in Pakistan will require an elaborate and multifaceted approach to include more than legislation. While reasonable efforts have been made in creating a legal framework, protection of victims and incrimination of the accused, putting laws into practical implementation is a real challenge. One of the impediments toward availing the victims of legal protections includes attitude, cultural normativeness, and systemic barriers. These include building public awareness, increasing the capacity of law enforcement and judicial authorities, and providing comprehensive support services for the victims. In so doing, Pakistan can go a long way toward the eradication of gender-based violence and move further down the road toward the equitable distribution of justice for all (UN Women, 2020).

Recommendations

- Intensify and mainstream training and sensitization for the police force and judicial officers.
- Amplify public sensitization campaigns to increase the level of knowledge among citizens about their rights and protections as enshrined in law.
- Intensify and strengthen monitoring and accountability mechanisms to ensure implementation of GBV laws.
- Avail resources and services for victims of violence, including shelters, legal aid, and counseling.
- Challenge and change patriarchal norms and attitudes through community engagements and dialogues.

- Work together with the government, NGOs, and the entire world on a well-coordinated and integrated approach on GBV.
- Regular monitoring and upgrading of the prevailing laws for their effectiveness and to be flexible enough to suit the victims' needs.

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